

GOOGLE ASSISTANT AI TECHNOLOGICAL TOOLS ON SCIENCE EDUCATION STUDENTS' ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT IN IGNATIUS AJURU UNIVERSITY, PORT HARCOURT

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Abstract

This study centered on the effect of Google assistant AI technological tools on science education students' academic achievement in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt. In course of the study, the pre-test post-test non-equivalent control group involving quasi-experimental design was used. Specifically, two objectives, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. The study was conducted using 100 to 400 Level Science education students of Ignatius Ajuru University. The study population was made up of one thousand eight hundred and five (1085), out of which a sample of ninety-two (92) was drawn from 300 level through a purposive sampling technique. Intact class was used and the students were randomly assigned by balloting, to experimental and control groups respectively. The experimental group was taught integration in science using Google assistant AI technological tools, while the control group was taught using the conventional (lecture) method. Science Achievement test (SAT) and lesson plan was the instruments for data collection. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the two research questions while t-test was used to test the two null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The results revealed among others that there exist statistically significant improvements in students' achievement after exposure to Google assistant AI technological tool. Consequently, the study held that there is a statistically significant difference in academic achievement between students exposed to Google assistant AI technological tool and lecture methods. Based on the finding and the conclusion the following recommendations among others were made that: Science education Lecturers should include Google Assistant AI into their lessons, as this approach can enhance students' academic achievements. The lecturers should ensure that both male and female students have equal access to Google Assistant AI in their lessons.

Keywords: Google Assistant, AI Technological Tools, Science Education, Students, Academic Achievement.

Introduction

Education is widely recognized by scholars as a fundamental instrument for knowledge transfer and societal advancement. It involves the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, and competencies while fostering critical thinking and practical application for individual and societal development (Dean, 2020). In today's rapidly evolving world, technology has become an essential component of organizational and institutional activities. Technological innovations have significantly transformed various sectors of

society, including education, agriculture, healthcare, and industry, contributing greatly to social and economic progress. However, despite these advancements, the availability and accessibility of technological devices in classrooms remain inadequate in many educational settings, raising concerns about the effective integration and utilization of technology in the teaching and learning process (Geneva, 2021).

Science Education is the application of educational concepts and theories to the effective teaching and learning of science in

schools (Adolphus 2022). As the world grows more towards being a global village, the need to innovate in teaching practices with particular reference to online teaching becomes imperative if attempt is to be made to bridge the gap between the developing and developed world. Biology, chemistry and Physics, as core science subjects, will continue to play a pivotal role in technological advancement and scientific development. They are compulsory subject for students pursuing careers in engineering, medicine, and other science-based disciplines.

In recent years, Artificial Intelligence (AI) has emerged as a transformative force in education. AI tools such as Google Assistant have been increasingly utilized to support teaching and learning processes. Google Assistant, a virtual AI tool, provides instant access to information, facilitates personalized learning experiences, and enhances students' problem-solving skills. Studies by Oladele and Ahmed (2021) have highlighted the potential of AI in fostering active learning and improving students' academic performance in science subjects. In the context of higher education, AI-driven technologies are

The integration of AI tools in teaching of science could provide an innovative approach to addressing learning difficulties. Google Assistant, for instance, allows students to interact with complex concepts through voice commands and real-time responses, making abstract ideas more relatable. As noted by Ijeoma and Olorunfemi (2022), the use of AI in classrooms promotes collaborative learning and boosts students' confidence in tackling challenging topics in science. Science Education play critical role in technological development, engineering, and environmental science. However, teaching and learning of sciences in Nigerian secondary schools have long been challenged by several factors, including poor teaching methods, limited access to laboratory equipment, large class

becoming indispensable tools for students, not only aiding their academic pursuits but also shaping the way they spend their leisure time (Chaudhary et al., 2024; Kamalov et al., 2023). From AI-powered learning platforms and personalized study assistants to entertainment apps and virtual communication tools, the role of AI in students' lives has become more significant than ever (Bhutoria, 2022). Students spend increasing amounts of time in front of their screens, relying on AI for a variety of tasks, often at the recommendation of their instructors, who encourage them to leverage these technologies for assignments and research purposes (Seo et al., 2021). In many cases, students turn to AI to find quick answers, automate processes, or personalize their learning experiences (Kamalov et al., 2023). Outside of academia, AI-driven tools play an equally substantial role in entertainment, with students using these systems to engage in social media, gaming and other form of digital interaction during their free time (Dwivedi et al., 2023).

sizes, and lack of motivation among students (Ikuomola & Yusuf, 2019).

These issues result in consistently low academic achievement in sciences across many regions.

Even so, gender imbalance in science education remains a pressing issue in Nigeria. For decades, studies have reported that male students outperform their female counterparts in subjects like physics, chemistry and Biology to sociocultural biases, lack of female role models in STEM, and disparities in confidence levels (Adedeji & Adeoye, 2019). These gaps are not solely academic but are influenced by gendered perceptions of science and access to learning resources. AI tools like Google Assistant may offer a level playing field by giving both male and female students equal

access to learning support, without the judgment or pressure often experienced in traditional classroom settings (Nagamurali, 2025). According to the research's conclusions, Google Assistant may be added to typical English as a foreign language (EFL) teaching techniques to enhance pronunciation and provide accessible language practice beyond the classroom. The study also emphasizes AI's role in enhancing autonomy and engagement, while emphasizing the significance of better management of accent variability and managing complex conversations. To overcome these barriers and expand the use of AI in language learning, future studies should investigate advancements in the field, such as improved conversational complexity and accent identification. Ultimately, Google Assistant proves to be a significant supplementary tool for EFL speaking practice; however, it yields the best results when strategically integrated with direct human interaction to achieve a more holistic approach to language learning. Academic achievement is a key indicator of educational effectiveness and student comprehension. It reflects not only the learner's performance but also the efficiency of the teaching method employed. With the emergence of AI technologies, questions arise regarding their ability to enhance academic achievement in comparison to conventional instructional methods.

Interestingly, Zudonu et al. (2024) Investigated the Effect of Artificial Intelligence on Chemistry and Physics Students' Achievement and Conceptual Change in Heat Change in SSS2 in Rivers State. Their study adopted quasi-experimental research design (a non-randomized pretest-post-test control). Purposive sampling technique was used to select 160 participants from sixteen senior secondary schools two (SSS2) Chemistry and Physics students in Rivers West Education Zone in Rivers State. Mean, standard deviation, percentage, column chart and pie

chart were used to answer the five research questions and independent sample t-test was used to test for the five hypotheses generated at 0.05 level of significance. Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) and Physics Achievement Test (PAT) together with Conceptual Understanding Test (CUT) were used to determine students' achievement and conceptual change. A structured interview was conducted with the students taught using AI base instruction to examine their experiences and perceptions towards AI-based instruction in heat change.

Using test-retest method and Kuder-Richardson's formula-21 yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.78. The results indicated that the Physics students achieved higher in the pretest and post-test with a mean score of 14.40 and 46.35, respectively, against that of the chemistry students taught heat change using AI-based instruction with 12.45 and a post-test score of 44.63 but there was no significant difference in their academic achievement as well as the conceptual change. However, there was a significant difference in the academic achievement and conceptual change between students who received AI-based instruction and those who received traditional instruction as the calculated P-value was less than the alpha value of 0.05.

Furthermore, the experiences and perception of the Chemistry and Physics students were generally positive towards the use of AI in the teaching and learning of heat change. The findings of the study provided valuable insights into the potential benefits of integrating AI into Science education, particularly biology, chemistry and physics. The integration of AI in Science education has the potential to transform traditional teaching methods, providing personalized and engaging learning experiences that promote achievement, conceptual change, and positive perceptions of the subjects. It was

recommended that further research be conducted to explore the long-term effects of AI-based instruction on students' achievement and conceptual change in heat change. Therefore, science educators should seize the advantage of AI to enhance students learning outcomes as AI has proven to have these potentials.

Ndo Ime Udoh (2024) researched on School Location and School Type as Determinants of Academic Performance of Senior School Biology Students Exposed to Chatbot AI or Expository Method. The study analyzed school location and school type as determinants of academic performance of senior secondary school biology students exposed to chatbot AI or expository method. The study adopted a quasi-experimental pretest post-test none randomize control group design. The research was conducted in Akwa Ibom State. The population of the study consisted of 30,985 Senior Secondary School two (SS2) students offering Biology as a subject in 227 Secondary schools in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria. A total number of 600 senior secondary school three male and female in sciences offering biology as a subject (280 males and 320 females) were divided into control and treatment groups.

The researcher developed instrument called Biology Performance Test (BPT). The instrument validation was done through content, and face validity. The researcher then incorporated all corrections into the work. Kuder-Richardson formula 21 test-retest methods were used to access the reliability at 0.05 level of reliability. Descriptive Statistics of Mean and Standard Deviation was used to present data for answering research questions. The study showed that urban and rural students performed equally high when exposed to Chatbot AI. And also, that mixed and single sex school students performed equally high when exposed to Chatbot AI. It was also revealed in the study that school location and

school type did not significantly affect academic performance in Biology of students exposed to Chatbot AI.

On this basis the study concluded that the utilization of Chatbot AI in teaching and learning Biology concepts is more effective than the use of traditional expository method because Chatbot AI engages students in interactive conversations provide immediate feedback and reinforce biological knowledge which can encourage critical thinking in the students thereby improving their academic performance in Biology. One of the recommendations made was that Akwa Ibom State governments should provide in-service training and professional development opportunities for educators to effectively utilize Chatbot AI technology in the classroom. This can lead to a more educated, updated and skilled workforce.

Statement of the Problem

The teaching and learning of science remain significant challenges for students and educators. Research has shown that students often struggle with abstract concepts, in science due to their complex and counterintuitive nature (Koponen & Mantyla, 2020). Despite its critical importance in the science curriculum, students often struggle with difficult concepts due to their abstract nature and the mathematical complexities involved. Artificial Intelligence (AI) may possibly have the potential to revolutionize Science Education by providing personalized and interactive learning experiences. However, there is a lack of evidence on its effectiveness in improving students' achievement in the University. Specifically, it is unknown whether the application of Google AI technological tools can enhance the academic achievement of students studying science Education in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education (IAUE) and whether it can address gender disparities in learning outcomes.

Interestingly, findings of studies on teaching and learning approaches consistently show a positive correlation between the application of Google AI technological tools and positive learning outcome. However, most of these studies were conducted in Secondary Schools (Chukundah, 2024) with little attention to our Nigeria University context. Furthermore, there is limited knowledge in existing literature as to whether the use of Google AI technological tools can aid the reduction of failure rate in students' academic achievements in science education. Thus, a gap exists in the literature that needs to be bridged. It is against this background of poor academic achievement that this study was set to focus on Google AI technological tools and science education students' academic achievements in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study is to investigate the effect of Google assistant AI technological tools on Science Education students' academic achievements in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education Port Harcourt. In specific term, the objectives specifically sought to:

- i. Find out the difference in students' academic achievement before and after they have been exposed to Google assistant AI.
- ii. Find out the difference in academic achievement between male and female students after being exposed to Google assistant AI.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- i. What is the academic achievement of students before and after they have been exposed to Google Assistant AI?
- ii. What is the academic achievement of the male and female students after they

have been exposed to Google Assistant AI?

Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were formulated and tested at 0.05 level of significance

HO₁: There is no significant difference between students' academic achievement before and after they have been exposed to Google assistant AI.

HO₂: There is no significant difference between male and female academic achievement after being exposed to Google assistant AI,

Research Method

The research adopted a quasi-experimental design specifically, a pre-test, post-test experimental and control group design to determine the effect of Google Assistant AI technological tools on academic achievement of Science Education Students in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rivers State. The population of the study was made up of all the one thousand eight hundred and five (1085) 100 to 400 level Science Education Students. Two intact classes were used and the students were randomly assigned by balloting to one experimental group and controlled group respectively. In all ninety-two (92) 200 Level Science Education students were recruited for the study.

The instrument for data collection was Science Achievement Test (SAT), and lesson plan using Google Assistant AI Technological Tool, lesson plan was designed using graphics, images and text in a power point presentation format to convey the sub-topics in integration in science The Science Achievement Test (PAT) was designed by drawing twenty-five (25) multiple choice questions from the topics. Each question attracts two (2) marks for

correct answer. A total of hundred (100) marks allocated to the instrument. The data generated from this instrument was used to answer the research questions and analyze the study hypotheses.

The research instrument received content and face validity by two (2) experts in the department of science education, faculty of education in Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt Rivers State. These experts validated the instrument in terms of face and content, ensuring: clarity of instrument to the respondents, clarity of language, lack of ambiguity, appropriateness and adequacy of the item in measuring what they are supposed to measure.

The instrument was trial tested with twenty (20) students of science education, Rivers State University, who will not be part of the main study but found to be equivalent in every aspect to the students that were used for the study. Items in Science Achievement Test (SAT) that passed the difficulty and discrimination test was certified suitable for the students and considered reliable enough for

the study. Test-retest method was used to estimate the reliability of co-efficient of 0.90. The Science Achievement Test (SAT) was administered as a pre-test to both the experimental and controlled group. The students in the experimental group were thought using Google Assistant AI Technological Tool and controlled group taught using lecture method.

After administrating pre-test and post-test of Science Achievement Test (SAT), the scores gathered were used for data analysis. The data analysis was done using descriptive statistics (mean) and standard deviation to answer research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significant.

Results

Each of the research questions and hypotheses were analyzed in their respective tables.

Presentation and Analysis of Data

Research Question One: What is the academic achievement of students before and after they are exposed to Google Assistant AI?

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of Google Assistant AI and conventional method on students' academic achievement

Group	N	Pretest		Posttest		Mean Gain
Conventional	38	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
		41.34	11.31	43.57	10.87	2.23
Experimental	54	41.20	9.84	61.06	8.20	19.86

The result in table 1 shows that the mean of students exposed to Google Assistant AI approach was 61.06 (post-test) while those with the conventional teaching method had a mean of 43.57 for post-test. The mean gain is 2.23 for the conventional and 19.86 for the Google Assistant AI approach. This means that students exposed to the Google Assistant AI

approach had a higher mean and performed better than the conventional teaching method.

Research Question Two: What is the academic achievement of the male and female students after they have been exposed to Google Assistant AI?

Table 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of mean performance scores of students using Google Assistant AI base on gender

GENDER	N	PRETEST		POSTTEST		MEAN GAIN
MALE	28	MEAN	SD	MEAN	SD	

		40.78	9.99	62.25	7.35	21.47
FEMALE	26	42.41	9.88	61.54	6.55	19.13

The results in table 2 shows that the performance of Male students exposed to the Google Assistant AI approach obtained a mean score of 62.25 while their Female counterparts had a performance means score of 61.54. Their mean gain was 21.47 for males and 19.13 for females. It is therefore deduced that the academic achievements of Male students had a higher mean score than the academic achievements of their Female

counterparts. Therefore, male students achieved better than female students in Google Assistant AI.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between students’ academic achievement before and after they have been exposed to Google assistant AI.

Table 3: Summary of t-test analysis of students’ academic achievement between Google assistant AI and conventional method

Group	N	Mean	SD	F	Df	Sign	Decision
Conventional	38	43.57	11.09	4.825	90	0.031	Rejected
Experimental	54	61.06	9.02				

Table 3 above shows that the P-value was (0.031) less than the significant level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was rejected. Meaning, there is a significant difference between students’ academic achievement before and after they have been exposed to Google assistant AI. However, with the

values of the mean, it is obvious that students performed better learning with Google assistant AI than the conventional approach.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between male and female academic achievement after being exposed to Google assistant AI.

Table 4.: Summary of t-test analysis between male and female academic achievement after being exposed to Google assistant AI

Gender	N	Mean	SD	F	Df	Sign	Decision
Male	28	62.25	8.67	0.660	50	0.420	Accepted
Female	26	61.54	8.22				

Table 4 above show that the P-value was (0.420) and that is more than the significant level of 0.05. Therefore, the null hypothesis was accepted. Meaning, there is no

significant difference between male and female students’ academic achievement after being exposed to Google assistant AI.

Discussion

The findings of this study were discussed in line with the research questions and hypotheses of the study in the following ways;
What is the academic achievement of students before and after they are exposed to Google Assistant AI?

The findings from table 1 and table 3 have shown that students exposed to the Google Assistant AI had a higher mean and achieved better than the conventional teaching method. Also, revealed a significant difference between students' academic achievement before and after they have been exposed to Google assistant AI.

This result is in line with studies conducted by Zudonu et al. (2024) who investigated the Effect of Artificial Intelligence on Chemistry and Physics Students' Achievement and Conceptual Change in Heat Change in SSS2 in Rivers State. The results indicated a significant difference in the academic achievement and conceptual change between students who received AI-based instruction and those who received traditional instruction as the calculated P-value was less than the alpha value of 0.05.

What is the academic achievement of the male and female students after they have been exposed to Google Assistant AI? The results in Table 2 deduced that male students performed a little better than female students in Google Assistant AI. But when subjected to significant test, table 4 shows no significant difference between male and female academic

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achievement after being exposed to Google assistant AI.

The outcome also harmonized with the findings of, Ndo Ime Udoh (2024) researched on School Location and School Type as Determinants of Academic Performance of Senior School Biology Students Exposed to Chatbot AI or Expository Method. The result shows no significant difference between genders on students' academic performance.”

Conclusions

In conclusion, there exist higher academic achievements of students exposed to Google Assistant AI. The use of Google Assistant AI in teaching led to significant performance improvements regardless of gender. In other words, Google Assistant AI enhanced learning and boosted academic achievements with no gender difference for all students.

Recommendations

The following recommendations were made based on findings and conclusions drawn from the study:

1. The use of Google assistant AI technological tools in instructional delivery in science education should be encouraged, since it facilitates academic achievement
2. NUC curriculum designers and publishers should have the use of Google assistant AI technological tools built into the curriculum of science education and text books, to ensure that the science lecturers adopt the instructional package.

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